

The role of non-governmental, non-profit organizations in the development of society

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Abstract: This article provides information about the mission, purpose, features, and capabilities of non-governmental non-commercial organizations. Opinions were expressed about the role of these organizations in the development of society.

Key words: non-governmental non-commercial organizations, legal entities, state, law, action strategy, civil society.

A non-governmental non-profit organization is a self-governing organization established on a voluntary basis by individuals and legal entities, which does not make income the main goal of its activity and does not distribute the received income among its participants [1]. Non-governmental non-profit organization to protect the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, other democratic values[2:1492-1495], to achieve social, cultural and educational goals, to satisfy spiritual and other non-material needs, to carry out charitable activities, and will be created for other socially beneficial purposes. The state ensures compliance with the rights and legal interests of non-governmental non-profit organizations, provides them with equal legal opportunities for participation in social life[3:135-138]. Non-governmental non-profit organizations can be established to achieve social, charitable, cultural-educational, political, scientific and administrative goals in the field of health protection of citizens, development of physical education and sports, satisfaction of spiritual and other intangible needs of citizens. It is created for the protection of the rights and legal interests of citizens and organizations [4:1-6], resolution of disputes and conflicts, provision of legal assistance, as well as other purposes aimed at achieving public interests.

Non-governmental non-profit organizations operating in our country help to protect national values, human rights and freedoms and [5:96-100] legal interests, increase the social and economic activity and legal culture of citizens, and ensure the balance of interests in society. The development of civil society institutions, increasing their social and political activity in the five priority areas of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 is defined as the main direction [6:121-123] of

improving the state and society. Today, non-governmental non-commercial organizations and other institutions of civil society are gaining importance in the way of establishing a democratic legal state, ensuring the rule of law in society and increasing the socio-political and economic potential of the country.

In order to further increase the role of non-governmental non-profit organizations as an active participant and partner in the reforms implemented in our republic, to strengthen the protection of their rights and legitimate interests, to expand the scope of state support [7:128-131] and to create favorable conditions for them several things are being done. Today, more than 10,000 non-governmental, non-profit organizations realize the noble idea that society is the initiator of reforms, protect the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, democratic values, social, cultural [8:128-132] and educational reforms. contributing to its implementation. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 3, 2021 "On additional measures to support non-governmental non-profit organizations by the state, to ensure the protection of their freedom of activity, rights and legal interests" is being implemented in this regard. It was another important step in expanding the scope of work, raising the status and position of civil society institutions[9:73-76]. The procedure for agreeing to receive funds and property from foreign persons to the NGO, which was later criticized by experts, motivated the organization of work in this direction[10] based on the needs of the times. Now, it is decided to increase the total amount of funds and property from foreign sources in one calendar year from twenty times to one hundred times the amount of the basic calculation by NGOs, after notifying the registration body. This serves to prevent excessive distraction in the work of public organizations, to expand the possibility of free activity and [11:59-63] to increase the potential of civil society institutions. Today, although the procedure for issuing a state social order for the implementation of socially important projects has been established by state administration bodies, this experience is hardly used in practice. Therefore, the public fund for the support of non-governmental non-profit organizations of Uzbekistan was assigned the task of allocating state subsidies for financing programs and projects aimed at the development of local NGOs. This innovation makes it possible to improve the practice of financing socially useful projects such as reducing poverty, creating new jobs[12:86-90] by issuing targeted social orders, and shows that NGOs are of great importance for the development of society.

Comprehensive measures aimed at strengthening the role of civil society institutions are being implemented in Uzbekistan[13:386-391]. As a result, today the

number of NGOs has increased by 16% and has exceeded 9,800, while the number of neighborhoods has reached almost 10,000. In terms of achieving political, social, economic, ecological, cultural and educational goals, as well as the implementation of national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development, the level of social partnership between state bodies and non-governmental non-profit organizations has risen to a fundamentally new level. "Friendship and NGO House" has been established in 11 regions of our country, and such houses are about to be opened in 3 more regions. In addition, 15 co-working centers have started working. The number of employees working on a permanent [14:292-296] basis in the system of non-governmental non-profit organizations has exceeded 52 thousand people. In the next period, the NGO is the sole source [15:26-28] and the author of People's Laws, and it is noticeable that it shows significant activity in implementing the principles that all important decisions are taken directly on the basis of dialogue with the people and taking into account public opinion.

In particular, more than 100 national and international forums on constitutional reforms were held by non-governmental non-commercial organizations under the leadership of the Constitutional Commission. For the first time, more than 200 national NGOs took an active part in the process of public, gender, child rights, protection of human rights and anti-corruption expertise of the draft Constitutional law. In short, it will serve to further increase the role of non-governmental non-profit organizations as an active participant and partner in the reforms implemented in our country, to expand the scope of their state support [16] and to strengthen their position in society. This is proof that the protection of human dignity, rights, and interests is at the top of the list in our country.

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